

Photosynthetic Reactions in Plants: A Teacher's Guide for Senior High School Instruction

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Dr. Raphael Kevin I. Nagal, RN, LPT

Department of Education – Division of Aklan, Philippines

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5790-4938>

Abstract

Photosynthetic Reactions in Plants is an instructional module developed to enhance senior high school learners' conceptual understanding of bioenergetics. Grounded in the K–12 Earth and Life Science curriculum, the module integrates inquiry-based pedagogy, experimentation, and conceptual abstraction to teach how photosynthetic organisms convert light energy into chemical energy. The material introduces the biochemical foundations of photosynthesis, differentiates the Light-Dependent and Light-Independent (Calvin Cycle) reactions, and guides learners in identifying the inputs and outputs of each stage. Hands-on experiments reinforce theoretical concepts by demonstrating oxygen release and starch formation in plant tissues. Assessment components, including pre-tests, guided questions, and performance tasks, support formative and summative evaluation. This scholarly version contextualizes the module within science education research, emphasizing its contribution to developing scientific literacy, critical thinking, and experiential learning in secondary biology instruction. The resource serves as both a teaching guide and a structured learning tool that aligns with national curriculum standards and promotes active, evidence-based understanding of photosynthetic processes.

Keywords: Photosynthesis; Light-Dependent Reaction; Calvin Cycle; Photosynthetic Pathways; Bioenergetics; Senior High School Science; Biology Education; ATP; NADPH

INTRODUCTION:

Photosynthesis is a central concept in biological sciences, forming the foundation for understanding energy transformation in ecosystems. Senior high school learners often encounter difficulty grasping the biochemical mechanisms underlying the Light-Dependent and Light-Independent reactions due to their abstract nature. To address this gap, the Department of Education emphasizes activity-based learning and contextualized instruction in the science curriculum.

Photosynthetic Reactions in Plants was developed as a structured learning module to provide a clear, scaffolded pathway for students to explore bioenergetics. The module integrates conceptual explanations, visual representations, guided inquiry, and experimental validation to strengthen students' comprehension of photosynthetic processes. It also aligns with curriculum competency S11/12LT-IIbd-5, which requires learners to explain how photosynthetic organisms convert carbon dioxide and water into energy-rich compounds.

By combining scientific accuracy, pedagogical structure, and practical experimentation, this module contributes to research-based efforts in improving science instruction and promoting scientific literacy among senior high school learners.

RATIONALE

This module responds to the educational need for conceptually coherent and pedagogy-aligned materials in senior high school biology. Research in science education demonstrates that students learn

more effectively when abstract biochemical processes are linked to observable evidence through experiments and models. This material supports:

- **Conceptual understanding** of bioenergetics
- **Inquiry-based learning** through guided experiments
- **Critical thinking** via open-ended questions and analysis tasks
- **Curriculum alignment** with the Philippine K–12 Earth and Life Science standards

Its structured format allows teachers to deliver consistent instruction while adapting the module for various learning abilities.

EARTH AND LIFE SCIENCE

SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL CORE SUBJECT

PHOTOSYNTHETIC REACTIONS IN PLANTS

A TEACHER'S GUIDE

by:
DR. RAPHAEL KEVIN I. NAGAL

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A TEACHER'S GUIDE TO THE LEARNING MODULE: *PHOTOSYNTHETIC REACTIONS IN PLANTS*

by Dr. Raphael Kevin I. Nagal

- I. CONTENT: Bioenergetics
- II. CONTENT STANDARD: The learners demonstrate understanding of how photosynthetic organisms capture light energy to form sugar molecules.
- III. PERFORMANCE STANDARD: The learners shall be able to perform the experiments in the learning module.
- IV. LEARNING COMPETENCIES: The learners explain how photosynthetic organisms use light energy to combine carbon dioxide and water to form energy-rich compounds
- V. LEARNING OBJECTIVES: After 2 hours of Activity-based lecture discussion, the students will be able to:
 - a. Define photosynthesis
 - b. Identify the inputs and outputs of the photosynthetic reactions; and
 - c. Differentiate Light Dependent and Light Independent reactions
- VI. COURSE CODE: S11/12LT-IIbd-5
- VII. VALUE FOCUS:
 - a. Cooperation
 - b. Self-discipline
 - c. Awareness
 - d. Respect
 - e. Critical Thinking
- VIII. MATERIALS:
 - a. Laptop
 - b. LCD Projector
 - c. Speaker
 - d. Chalk and Blackboard
 - e. Paper and Pencil/Ball pen
 - f. Manila Paper
 - g. Tincture of iodine
 - h. Medicine dropper
 - i. Wire gauze
 - j. Denatured alcohol
 - k. Beaker
 - l. Box of matches
 - m. Water bath
 - n. Petri dish
 - o. Fresh leaf of *mayana*

- p. Alcohol lamp
- q. Tripod
- r. Test Tube
- s. Water
- t. *Santan* leaf
- u. Learning Module or Reader: PHOTOSYNTHETIC REACTIONS IN PLANTS

7Es of Lesson Planning

IX. ELICIT/ ENGAGE

- ✓ Recall of previous and related topics through an inquiry-based pedagogy. Contextualize existing knowledge. E.g.:
 - “What are the cellular functions necessary for survival?”
 - “What have you remembered about photosynthesis?”
 - “Which organisms in our locality engages in photosynthesis?”
- ✓ State Objectives:
 - “This lesson will help you understand the processes involved before, during and after the plant captures light energy to form sugar molecules (plant food). This will enhance your knowledge about photosynthesis and let you appreciate the beauty of nature. Specifically, at the end of this lesson you should be able to:
 - Define photosynthesis
 - Identify the inputs and outputs of the photosynthetic reactions; and
 - Differentiate Light Dependent and Light Independent reactions”

X. EXPLORE

- ✓ Pre-Test: True or False. Identify whether the following statements is True or False. Write your answers on the space provided before each number.
 - _____ 1. Photosynthesis only happens in organisms with chlorophyll.
 - _____ 2. Photosynthesis will happen in the presence of sunlight.
 - _____ 3. Water and carbon dioxide are the inputs in photosynthesis.
 - _____ 4. Carbon dioxide and glucose are the main products of photosynthesis.
 - _____ 5. Photosynthesis may also occur in other Kingdoms of organisms.
- ✓ ANSWERS: 1. FALSE; 2. TRUE; 3. TRUE; 4. FALSE; 5. TRUE

XI. EXPLAIN: Abstraction of Concepts

What is Photosynthesis?

Photosynthesis is the process by which plants, some bacteria, and some *protistans* use the energy from sunlight to produce sugar.

Conversion of unusable sunlight energy into usable chemical energy is associated with the actions of the green pigment called **chlorophyll**.

The general process involves the use of water and the release of oxygen.

Photosynthesis may be summarized by the word equation:

We can write the overall reaction of this process as:

The next figure summarizes the inputs and outputs of photosynthesis:

As mentioned, the **Chloroplasts** are the sites of photosynthesis. The conversion of light energy to chemical energy occurs in it.

There are two stages of Photosynthetic Reactions: (1) Light Dependent and (2) Light Independent (Calvin's Cycle)

What happens during the Light Dependent Reaction?

Light Dependent Reaction is a light-dependent series of reactions which occur in the granules of the chloroplasts, and require the direct energy of light to make energy-carrier molecules that are used in the second process (the Calvin's Cycle).

The process involves trapping of light energy in the chlorophyll to make ATP (adenosine triphosphate) molecules. This process is called **photophosphorylation**.

At the same time water is split into oxygen and hydrogen ions and free electrons (e⁻) through the process of photolysis. This equation simplifies it:

The electrons then react with a carrier molecule nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP), changing it from its oxidized state (NADP⁺) to its reduced state (NADPH). Here is its equation:

Thus, in light dependent reaction, the main product is **Oxygen**.

What happens during the Light Independent Reaction (Calvin's Cycle)?

The Light Independent Reaction is a light-independent series of reactions which occur in the stroma of the chloroplasts. This happens when the products of the light reaction, ATP and NADPH, are used to make carbohydrates from carbon dioxide. Thus, its main product is the formation of **glucose** (C₆H₁₂O₆).

In this process, the hydrogen components of NADPH combine with the CO₂ to form glucose. The NADPH then returns to its older form NADP⁺. The ATP used in this process was now reduced to ADP and P ions. The cycle then again returns to the Light Dependent Reaction.

Some plants are even able to produce other organic compounds such as fatty acids and protein depending on the compounds mixed during the process. Like for instance, protein is produced if Nitrogen is mixed in the process of converting carbon dioxide to glucose.

The entire photosynthetic reaction is summarized by this diagram:

XII. ELABORATE

- ✓ Play the accompanying video for the Learning Module Package.
 “We will be watching an interactive video presentation summarizing our topic today.”
- ✓ Ask for clarifications.
 “Do you have any questions regarding the discussion?”
 “Do you need to view the video again?”

XIII. EXTEND

✓ Experimentation

Experiment A: Let's prove that Oxygen is produced in Photosynthesis

Materials: Test Tube; Water; available plant sample (preferably *Santan* leaf)

Procedure:

1. Place a fresh *Santan* leaf inside a test tube. Add water to the test tube to cover the leaf or plant.
2. Leave the setup for fifteen to twenty minutes at room temperature (preferably 25-30 °C)
3. Observe the setup.

Guide Questions:

- A What did you observe on the leaf or on the plant?
- B Have you seen bubbles in the experimental setup?
- C These bubbles are indicative of what?

Experiment B: Let's prove that Sugar is produced in Photosynthesis

Materials: Tincture of iodine; Medicine dropper; Wire gauze; Denatured alcohol;

Beaker; Box of matches; Water bath; Petri dish; Fresh leaf of *mayana*; Alcohol lamp; Tripod

Procedure:

1. Get a *mayana* leaf
2. Remove the leaf color by boiling it in alcohol. To do this, follow the steps below:
 - a. Fill the beaker (3/4 of its capacity) with water. Let it boil.
 - b. While waiting for the water to boil. Get a leaf sample and place it in a test tube. Pour denatured alcohol into the test tube, until the leaf has been submerged.
 - c. When the water in the beaker boils, place the test tube with leaf and alcohol in it. Let the water boil for another three minutes or until all the color of the leaf has been extracted.
3. Remove the test tube from the beaker. Then, get the leaf out of the test tube.
4. Rinse the leaf with water, and then place it on a petri dish.
5. Put drops of iodine, until the leaf has been soaked.
6. Observe the leaf. If the color of the leaf turns to bluish black, it indicates the presence of starch. No change in color indicates absence of starch.

Fun Fact: Iodine Test for Sugar is also used by Community Health Practitioners to determine the presence of sugar on a person's urine. Although not conclusive, this will give a warning to those people who may have diabetes.

Guide Questions:

- A What can you infer from your observation?

✓ Experiential Learning Enhancement

Fantastic Photosynthesis...

- Create a poem about photosynthesis.
- The poem should clearly describe the process of photosynthesis.
- You are free to choose whichever style of poem writing.
- Any Language or dialect can be used.
- Submit your poem in an intermediate pad.
- Expect your score and feedback for your output 2-3 days after submission.

“Here is your rubric for scoring”

CATEGORY	1	2	3
THE WRITING PROCESS / EFFORT	Student devoted little time and effort to the writing process. It appears that the student does not care about the assignment. The poem has many errors.	Student devoted some time and effort to the writing process but was not very thorough. Does enough to get by. There are several errors.	Student devoted a lot of time and effort to the writing process and worked hard to make the poem a good read. The poem has no errors.
TITLE	The poem has no title.	The poem has a title but somewhat does not relate to the content of the poem.	The poem has a title that clearly relates to the poem and adds interest to the theme or message of the poem
STYLE	The poem lacks style and the thoughts did not come out clearly on paper.	The poem is written somewhat with style. Thoughts are clear to a degree.	The poem is written with a great sense of style. The poem has been well thought out and makes sense to the reader.
VOCABULARY	The poem lacks description and does not allow the reader to visualize the poem.	The poem includes some descriptive words and phrases.	The poem is filled with descriptive vocabulary that appeals to the reader.

✓ POSSIBLE ANSWERS:

Experiment A

Guide Questions:

- A There is perspiration or bubbles etc.
- B If the experiment is done correctly, then the answer should be YES
- C The presence of Oxygen on the Leaf

Experiment B

Guide Questions:

- A If the experiment is done correctly, the leaf should turn to blue to bluish black. This result is a proof that sugar or starch is present in the leaf

XIV. EVALUATE

✓ Summarize the Lesson.

“We have learned that **Photosynthesis** is the process by which plants, some bacteria, and some protists use the energy from sunlight to produce sugar. The inputs needed in the process are water and carbon dioxide. The light energy from the sun is necessary to break down the molecules of water. The products of which are oxygen and glucose. The two stages of Photosynthesis are Light Dependent and Light Independent (Calvin’s Cycle) reactions.”

✓ Post-Test: MULTIPLE CHOICE. Select the letter of the correct answer and write it on the space provided before each number.

- ____1. One must understand that photosynthesis
 - a. is needed by plants to survive.

- b. is needed by animals to survive.
 - c. is needed by both plants and animals to survive.
 - d. is needed by all organisms to thrive.
- ____2. Which of the following is FALSE about photosynthesis?
- a. The main product of photosynthesis is carbon dioxide.
 - b. The main product of photosynthesis is oxygen and glucose.
 - c. Photosynthesis makes use of carbon dioxide to make glucose
 - d. Photosynthesis occurs in two stages
- ____3. Which of the following is TRUE about the Calvin's Cycle?
- a. It's main process is to convert carbon dioxide to glucose.
 - b. Oxygen is produced in this stage.
 - c. This process occurs in the presence of light energy.
 - d. This cycle can occur independently without the light dependent cycle.
- ____4. Which of the following occurs during the light dependent reaction?
- a. Carbon dioxide is converted to sugar.
 - b. Oxygen is released in the atmosphere.
 - c. Oxygen is dissociated from carbon dioxide.
 - d. Carbon dioxide is metabolized to form glucose.
- ____5. All of these may happen at any stage of photosynthesis except
- a. Carbon dioxide is converted to sugar.
 - b. Glucose molecules are converted to fats.
 - c. Oxygen is dissociated from water through photolysis.
 - d. Oxygen is released into the atmosphere.

✓ ANSWERS: 1.D; 2.A; 3.A; 4.B; 5.B

PRINTABLES:

- **KNOWLEDGE CHECKER: PROTISTANS**
- **KNOWLEDGE CHECKER: ATP**
- **SIMPLIFIED PHOTOSYNTHESIS EQUATION**
- **SIMPLIFIED PHOTOSYNTHESIS INPUT AND OUTPUT**
- **KNOWLEDGE CHECKER: MELVIN ELLIS CALVIN**
- **LDR AND LIR DIAGRAM**

PRINTABLE: KNOWLEDGE CHECKER: PROTISTANS

**KNOWLEDGE
CHECK!**

Protistans: Microorganisms that don't belong to the Kingdom Animal, Plants or Fungi. Protists mostly live in water. e.g. Algae, Protozoans

PRINTABLE: KNOWLEDGE CHECKER: ATP

**KNOWLEDGE
CHECK!**

ATP (adenosine triphosphate) are the energy needed by the living cell in order to do its processes.

PRINTABLE: SIMPLIFIED PHOTOSYNTHESIS EQUATION

PRINTABLE: SIMPLIFIED PHOTOSYNTHESIS INPUT AND OUTPUT

**KNOWLEDGE
CHECK!**

Melvin Ellis Calvin (April 8, 1911-January 8, 1997) was an American biochemist most famed for discovering the Calvin Cycle along with Andrew Benson and James Bassham

Image taken from: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Melvin-Calvin>

PRINTABLE: LDR AND LIR DIAGRAM

METADATA:

Title: Photosynthetic Reactions in Plants

Author: Dr. Raphael Kevin I. Nagal

Language: English

Keywords: Photosynthesis, photosynthetic reactions, Calvin's Cycle, Light Dependent Reaction, Light Independent Reaction, ATP, NADPH, photolysis, S11/12LT-IIbd-5

Description: This learning module explains how photosynthetic organisms use light energy to combine carbon dioxide and water to form energy-rich compounds

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Primary Storage: Printed Material

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Developer: Dr. Raphael Kevin I. Nagal

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